

Investigation of neodymium complex with acid chrome blue K by beta-correction spectrophotometry

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The neodymium complex with acid chrome blue K (ACBK) at pH 10 has been studied in detail by beta-correction spectrophotometry. The cationic surfactant, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) is useful for increasing the sensitivity and solubility of ligand and complex. The characteristic factors of complex are calculated, for example, complex ratio and stability constant. Results show that $\text{Nd}(\text{ACBK})_3$ is formed and its real not apparent molar absorptivity is the first to be determined as follows : $\epsilon_{\text{Nd}(\text{ACBK})_3}^{520} = 5.54 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at pH 10. In addition, the cumulative stability constant of complex $\text{Nd}(\text{ACBK})_3$ is still computed to be 1.72×10^{16} in ionic strength 0.1 M and at temperature 15°.

The azo-ligand, acid chrome blue K (ACBK) is a conventional indicator for complexing calcium¹, copper² etc. but has never been used to complex rare earth elements. In this report, the investigation of Nd complex with ACBK is first made by beta-correction spectrophotometry³ which eliminates the interference of the excess ligand on absorbance of Nd complex. It is found that Nd^{III} is sensitive to complex ACBK at pH 10 in the presence of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB). The beta-correction spectrophotometric results show that the formed complex is expressed by $\text{Nd}(\text{ACBK})_3$ and its real absorptivity is equal to $\epsilon_{\text{Nd}(\text{ACBK})_3}^{520} = 5.54 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ but its apparent one only $3.67 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. In addition, the beta-correction method is still applied for the determination of stepwise and cumulative stability constants. The operation is simpler and the result is more acceptable than other conventional methods, such as molar ratio, continuous variation, equilibrium movement and so on, because it gives the accurate absorption of Nd complex product. On the contrary, the conventional methods are often limited because of the effect of the excess of ligand.

Principle :

From the following expression³ the real absorbance (A_c) of a metal (M) complex (ML_γ) produced with a ligand (L) in solution, is calculated,

$$A_c = \frac{\Delta A - \beta \Delta A'}{1 - \alpha \beta}$$

where ΔA and $\Delta A'$ are the absorbances of the mixed solution of ML_γ and L measured at wavelengths λ_2 and λ_1 against the reagent blank (only L solution), respectively, and both α and β are named correction factors which are calculated as

$$\alpha = \frac{\epsilon_{\text{ML}_\gamma}^{\lambda_1}}{\epsilon_{\text{ML}_\gamma}^{\lambda_2}}$$

and

$$\beta = \frac{\epsilon_L^{\lambda_2}}{\epsilon_L^{\lambda_1}}$$

where $\epsilon_{\text{ML}_\gamma}^{\lambda_1}$, $\epsilon_{\text{ML}_\gamma}^{\lambda_2}$, $\epsilon_L^{\lambda_1}$ and $\epsilon_L^{\lambda_2}$ are the molar absorptivities of ML_γ and L at wavelengths λ_1 and λ_2 , respectively, whose ratio may be computed after the direct determination of L and ML_γ solutions.

The true not apparent molar absorptivity ($\epsilon_{\text{ML}_\gamma}^{\lambda_2}$) and the amount (γ') of L to coordinate M in reaction may be expressed as

$$\epsilon_{\text{ML}_\gamma}^{\lambda_2} = \frac{A_c}{\delta C_M}$$

and

$$\eta = \frac{A_c - \Delta A}{A_0}$$

$$\gamma' = \eta \frac{C_L}{C_M}$$

where η is the reacted ratio of ligand, C_M the molar concentration (mol dm^{-3}) of M in the beginning, δ the thickness of the cell, C_L the molar concentration (mol dm^{-3}) of L in the beginning and A_0 the absorbance of the blank reagent (only L) measured at wavelength λ_2 against water reference. While γ' reaches maximum, then $\gamma = \gamma'$, where γ is a natural number to be named the complex number or stoichiometric ratio of the complex formed. In addition, the following expression was the first to be established for determination of the n -th stage ($0 < n < \gamma$) stability constant (K_n) of complex ML_γ from the reaction equation : $\text{ML}_{n-1} + \text{L} \rightleftharpoons \text{ML}_n$, which must use such a M-L solution to form the complexation ratio γ' between $n-1$ and n ,

$$K_n = \frac{\gamma' + 1 - n}{(n - \gamma') (C_L - \gamma' C_M)}$$

From each K_n we can further calculate the cumulative constant (K) of complex ML_γ .

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra : The color reaction of neodymium with ACBK at pH 10 was measured. Results show the peak absorption at wavelength λ_1 630 nm and the valley absorption at λ_2 520 nm from which α and β are calculated. The following equation was used : $A_c = 1.07(\Delta A - 0.494\Delta A')$.

Effect of ligand concentration : Plots of addition of ACBK solution against the absorbance of neodymium complexed solution reveal that the positive and negative absorption approached maximum when the addition of ACBK solution was over 2.0 ml. It is difficult to complete the complexation ratio of ACBK to Nd by molar ratio method because of unclear inflexion point. From the curves, the real absorbance (A_c) of neodymium complex solution and complexation ratio (γ') of ACBK to Nd can be calculated in each concentration of ACBK. It has been found that the maximal γ' approaches 3 when the addition of 0.500 mmol dm⁻³ ACBK is over 1.5 ml. Therefore, the following complex Nd(ACBK)₃ was formed in presence of CTAB at pH 10. The apparent and real molar absorptivity of Nd(ACBK)₃ are calculated to be 3.67×10^4 and 5.54×10^4 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 520 nm, respectively.

Effect of pH : The reaction of Nd with ACBK in presence of CTAB gave maximal absorption at pH 9–10.5, hence in this study, pH 10 was selected.

Effect of surfactant selection and addition : CTAB gives maximal absorption, which is seven times more than that in the absence of surfactant. Also maximal absorption was observed when the addition of 5% CTAB was over 0.5 ml.

Effect of color-developed time : The study on the effect of reaction time reveals that absorbance reaches maximal and remains almost constant when the time is over 20 min.

Stability constant (K) : The following solutions were used for the determination of stability constant of Nd-ACBK complex at pH 10 : 0.139 μ mol/25 ml Nd^{III} with 0.150, 0.350 and 0.600 μ mol/25 ml ACBK in the presence of CTAB. From the equation, the stepwise and cumulative stability constants (K_s) were calculated (Table 1).

Table 1. Stability constant of Nd(ACBK)₃ at pH 10
Temp. = 15°, ionic strength = 0.1 M, amount of Nd = 0.139 μ mol/25 ml

Sl. no.	Amount of ACBK added	Absorbance		γ'	K
		$\Delta A'$	ΔA		
1.	0.150 μ mol/25 ml	-0.038	0.023	0.651	$K_1 = 7.81 \times 10^5$
		-0.039	0.025	0.589	$K_1 = 5.25 \times 10^5$
2.	0.350 μ mol/25 ml	-0.100	0.085	1.65	$K_2 = 3.84 \times 10^5$
		-0.102	0.078	1.61	$K_2 = 3.09 \times 10^5$
3.	0.600 μ mol/25 ml	-0.146	0.140	2.35	$K_3 = 0.49 \times 10^5$
		-0.158	0.134	2.51	$K_3 = 1.03 \times 10^5$
					$K = 1.72 \times 10^{16}$

Experimental

Absorbance was measured on a Shimadzu UV-3000 spectrophotometer with 1 cm cell.

Aqueous acid chrome blue K (ACBK, Shanghai Reagents) solution (0.5 mmol dm⁻³) was prepared in distilled water. Neodymium solution (500.0 mg dm⁻³) was prepared by dissolving neodymium sesquioxide (A.R., Shanghai Reagent) (0.857 g) in conc. HCl (10 ml) and diluted to 1000 ml with distilled water; a 10.0 mg dm⁻³ Nd solution was prepared before used. The buffer solution (pH 10) was prepared with ammonia (A.R., Beijing Chemical) and ammonium chloride (A.R., Shanghai Chemical). The anion surfactant, sodium dodecylbenzene sulfonate (SDS, Shanghai Reagents), nonionic surfactant, emulsifier OP (Beijing Chemicals) and cationic surfactant, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB, Shanghai Reagents) solutions (all 5%) were prepared for increasing the solubility of ligand and sensitivity of complexed reaction.

Procedure. Nd-ACBK complexed reaction : To a solution of Nd (20 μ g) were added buffer solution (2 ml) and 5% CTAB (1 ml). The addition of 0.500 mmol dm⁻³ ACBK solution was varied, then diluted to 25 ml with distilled water and mixed well. After 20 min, absorbances were measured at two wavelengths 630 and 520 nm.

References

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